

Development and Improvement of the Quadratic Depletion Method

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ABSTRACT

In nuclear reactor depletion calculations, the traditional predictor-corrector (PC) method requires two transport calculations per burnup step. However, in high-fidelity calculations, these two transport calculations significantly reduce the computational efficiency, especially for reactors reloaded with gadolinium (Gd)-bearing fuels, which require a much finer depletion step. The quadratic depletion (QD) method skips the corrector-step transport calculation and employs quadratic interpolation combined with a post-correction method to preserve accuracy. Nevertheless, the traditional QD method requires an excessive number of substeps to maintain precision, leading to high computational costs. To address this issue, a novel two-level predictor-corrector QD (TL-PC-QD) method is proposed to reduce the number of substeps. Comparative applications to Gd-bearing cases show that the TL-PC-QD method significantly reduces the number of substeps of the traditional QD method.

Keywords: Quadratic depletion, Post-correction, Gadolinium isotopes, substep

1. INTRODUCTION

The depletion calculation module serves as an important component in the nuclear reactor analysis codes. The traditional predictor-corrector (PC) method is one of the most widely used neutronics depletion coupling methods. In the traditional PC method, it is assumed that the microscopic reaction rates are constant in each depletion step; the bias caused by this assumption is acceptable in most cases. However, the bias is not negligible when it comes to strong neutron absorber isotopes like Gadolinium (Gd), because the reaction rates of Gd isotopes change dramatically with the number densities. A much smaller depletion step size has to be applied. It causes an increased number of transport and burnup calculations, thereby reducing overall computational efficiency.

Some other methods have been proposed to improve the accuracy for the depletion of Gd isotopes, such as the Projected predictor-corrector (PPC) method [1] and the Log linear rate (LLR) method [2]. Additionally, a comparison of various depletion methods is conducted, revealing the advances of the high-order methods [3][4].

However, all these depletion methodologies still require two flux calculations per step, imposing substantial computational costs, especially for the high-fidelity codes. The reaction rates fitting method is employed in previous work [5]. However, this method exhibits marginally lower accuracy than the PC method, especially for Gd-bearing fuel problems.

The quadratic depletion (QD) method achieves favorable performance in both computational efficiency and solution accuracy by omitting flux calculations in the corrector step and leveraging reaction-rate interpolation. The QD method assumes that the reaction rates of Gd isotopes are a quadratic function of ^{155}Gd , and the post-correction method omits the flux calculation in the corrector step by post-correcting the number density from previous burnup steps [6]. Both approaches are also applied in the high-fidelity neutronics code NECP-X [7] in this paper. In the QD method, the substep method is employed to implement the quadratic interpolation of reaction rates, where the numerical accuracy demonstrates significant dependence on the number of substeps. However, this enhancement in accuracy comes at the cost of linearly increasing computational time for burnup calculations. The two-

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level predictor-corrector QD (TL-PC-QD) method is proposed in this paper to acquire both precision and efficiency.

2. METHODOLOGY

This section presents the QD method incorporating the post-correction method and the TL-PC-QD method.

2.1. Traditional QD Method

In the traditional PC method, two burnup and flux calculations are needed. The reaction rates are calculated by the transport calculations at the predictor and corrector steps. The nuclide number densities from the predictor step and the corrector step are obtained by burnup calculations, and the average of the two is the final number densities for the next burnup step. Moreover, since dual flux calculations are computationally expensive, omitting the corrector flux calculation in the normal cases improves the efficiency while maintaining numerical accuracy [8].

The reaction rates of each depletion step are assumed to be constant in the PC method, which introduces negligible deviations in normal fuel cases. However, it exhibits significant deviations in Gd-bearing fuel due to the huge absorption cross sections of Gd isotopes. The QD method is developed based on the PC method and is selectively implemented in the corrector steps for only Gd isotopes. It is noticed that the microscopic reaction rates of the Gd isotopes are smooth functions of the ^{155}Gd number density. And the functions are assumed to be quadratic functions in the QD method [9]. The reaction rates of Gd isotopes can be calculated as

$$R_{m,n} = a_{m,n}N_{3,n}^2 + b_{m,n}N_{3,n} + c_{m,n}. \quad (1)$$

where $a_{m,n}$, $b_{m,n}$, $c_{m,n}$ are three coefficients at t_n for the m -th Gd isotope (m is from 1 to 7, for ^{152}Gd , ^{154}Gd , ^{155}Gd , ^{156}Gd , ^{157}Gd , ^{158}Gd , ^{160}Gd) and $N_{3,n}$ is the number density of the third Gd isotope ^{155}Gd .

The three coefficients can be determined by $R_{m,n-1}, N_{3,n-1}, R_{m,n}, N_{3,n}$ and $R_{m,n+1}^p, N_{m,n+1}^p$. $R_{m,n-1}, N_{3,n-1}, R_{m,n}, N_{3,n}$ are from the corrector step at t_{n-1} and t_n while $R_{m,n+1}^p$ and $N_{m,n+1}^p$ are from the predictor calculation at t_{n+1} . The coefficients subsequently enable precise calculation of microscopic reaction rates for Gd isotopes in each depletion region. And the QD method employs multiple substeps to consider the quadratic variation within two burnup steps, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. QD interpolation.

As mentioned above, for the normal fuel depletion calculations, the flux calculation can be omitted in the corrector step to improve efficiency, because the reaction rates vary slightly with the number densities. However, in Gd-bearing fuel cases, omitting the second flux calculation results in a significant error. Furthermore, the predictor number densities and reaction rates are also insufficiently accurate for determining the three coefficients. The post-correction method is developed to solve the problems.

The post-correction method assumes that the ratio of the reaction rates in the predictor and corrector steps is constant between the two adjacent time steps, which can be expressed as

$$f_n \equiv \frac{\ln(N_n^c/N_{n-1}^c)}{\ln(N_n^p/N_{n-1}^c)} = \frac{R_n^c}{R_n^p} \cong \frac{R_{n+1}^c}{R_{n+1}^p}. \quad (2)$$

where f_n is defined as the post-correction factor. And the post-corrected number densities can be calculated by:

$$N_{n+1}^{p,u} = N_n^c \exp [\ln(N_{n+1}^p/N_n^c) \times f_n]. \quad (3)$$

where u stands for post-correction. The post-correction factor for the next step is calculated as:

$$f_n = \frac{\ln(N_n^c/N_{n-1}^c)}{\ln(N_n^{p,u}/N_{n-1}^c)}. \quad (4)$$

And the predictor reaction rates $R_{n+1}^{p,u}$ calculated by transport calculation exhibit superior accuracy compared to R_{n+1}^p without post-correction.

Figure 2 illustrates the complete procedure for Gd-bearing fuel depletion calculation. The Gd isotopes are processed using the QD method, as depicted in Figure 2(a). The predictor step follows the conventional depletion method but incorporates the post-correction before the transport calculation. In the corrector step, quadratic depletion calculations are performed for Gd isotopes. The transport calculation in the corrector step is omitted, with the eigenvalue solutions for the next burnup step derived from the predictor step. Meanwhile, all other isotopes are calculated using the traditional PC method as shown in Figure 2(b). It is worth noting that despite the distinct calculation methods applied to Gd and non-Gd isotopes, all isotopes are still coupled together within the burnup calculation.

Figure 2. QD method and post-correction.

2.2. TL-PC-QD Method

In the traditional substep approach for the QD method, the micro reaction rates are assumed constant in each substep, introducing approximation error. Figure 3(a) demonstrates a significant degradation in accuracy with varying numbers of substeps in the QD calculations. Taking the results of the QD method with 200 substeps as the reference, the method requires a minimum of 100 substeps to achieve convergent solutions. This stringent requirement on the number of substeps substantially increases the computational cost of the traditional QD method.

The TL-PC-QD method is proposed to solve the problem. The TL-PC-QD method adopts a similar concept to the PPC method. Unlike most depletion methods typically applying the predictor-corrector approach solely in each burnup step, the TL-PC-QD method reimplements this approach at the substep level for the quadratic interpolation. Figure 4 illustrates the whole procedure of TL-PC-QD calculation. In the predictor substep, the procedure is the same as the traditional method, and the predictor substep

number density $N_{n,i+1}^{S,p}$ is obtained. In the corrector substep, the corrector substep reaction rate is calculated by $N_{n,i+1}^{S,p}$ using formula (1). And the corrector substep number density $N_{n,i+1}^{S,c}$ is calculated in the corrector substep point-depletion. The final substep number density $N_{n,i+1}^S$ is calculated by

$$N_{n,i+1}^S = (N_{n,i+1}^{S,p} + N_{n,i+1}^{S,c})/2. \quad (5)$$

The results indicate that the TL-PC-QD method exhibits minimal sensitivity to the number of substeps, with merely 5 substeps sufficiently to achieve the required precision, as presented in Figure 3(b). This optimization reduces burnup calculation time by 95% compared to the traditional QD method, which requires over 100 substeps.

Figure 3. Bias of different substeps for QD in the single Gd-bearing pin case.

Figure 4. Substep methods in the traditional QD and the TL-PC-QD method.

3. VERIFICATION

The TL-PC-QD method is implemented in the high-fidelity code NECP-X and compared with the PC method and the traditional QD method in various cases. The eigenvalues and power distribution results are shown in different problems. In all the following cases, the PC method and the TL-PC-QD method employ 5 substeps, while the traditional QD method utilizes 100 substeps to maintain required accuracy. Reference is the results of the traditional PC method using 100 MWd/tU burnup step.

3.1. The Gd-bearing Fuel Pin-cell Problem

Figure 5 illustrates the geometry of the Gd-bearing pin-cell. The fuel region contains 1.76 w/o ^{235}U and 9.0 w/o Gd_2O_3 . Ten equally-spaced rings are divided in the fuel region of the Gd-U pin to improve the accuracy of Gd's depletion.

Figure 5. Geometry of the Gd-bearing pin.

Figure 6 depicts the k_{eff} bias of different depletion methods using 500 MWd/tU burnup step. The maximum bias of the PC method is -985 pcm, which is entirely unacceptable. For the traditional QD method, the maximum bias is -273 pcm, whereas that of the TL-PC-QD method is only -122 pcm. Figure 7 illustrates the ^{155}Gd concentration differences in the innermost (Ring 1) and outermost (Ring 10) fuel regions. In Ring 1, the error increases rapidly with the burnup for the traditional PC method, the TL-PC-QD method maintains an error of less than 1% throughout the depletion calculation. Even with 100 substeps, the traditional QD method still exhibits a maximum error of 4.4%. In Ring 10, the error is less pronounced, which can be attributed to the relatively low power in this region; however, the traditional PC method still yields a maximum error of 3.54% at 8 GWd/tU.

Figure 6. K_{eff} bias for single Gd-bearing pin depletion.

Figure 7. ^{155}Gd concentration difference using different methods.

Table I summarizes the computational time for different methods in this case. Compared to the conventional PC method, the traditional QD method achieves a 50% efficiency improvement, while the TL-PC-QD method demonstrates an 87% improvement.

The results show that the TL-PC-QD method can not only reduce the number of substeps but also significantly improve the accuracy.

Table I. Time summary in single Gd-bearing pin case.

Depletion method	PC	QD	TL – PC – QD
Time/s	227.5	151.6	121.6
Accelerate ratio	/	1.50	1.87

3.2. The 2D Gd-bearing Fuel Assembly Problem

Figure 8 illustrates the geometry of a 2D Gd-bearing fuel assembly with 17x17 pin-cells. Each normal fuel rod contains 3.2 w/o ^{235}U . The orange circles represent the Gd-bearing fuel rods containing 1.76 w/o ^{235}U and 9.0 w/o Gd_2O_3 .

Figure 8. Geometry of the Gd-bearing assembly.

Figure 9 depicts the k_{eff} bias of different depletion methods using 500 MWd/tU burnup step. The maximum bias of the PC method is -188 pcm, whereas the maximum biases of the traditional QD method and the TL-PC-QD method are only -33 pcm and -30 pcm, respectively. Figure 10 illustrates the pin power difference for the different methods. The maximum pin power difference of the PC method reaches -0.33% in a Gd-bearing fuel pin region, because the burnup of the Gadolinium isotopes is severely underestimated. In contrast, the maximum power differences of the traditional QD and the TL-PC-QD are both less than 0.06% demonstrating the high accuracy in the burnup calculation of Gd isotopes.

Figure 9. K_{eff} bias for 2D Gd-bearing fuel assembly.

Figure 10. Pin power difference at 12 GWd/tU using different methods.

Table II summarizes the computational time for different methods in this case. Due to the large number of substeps required, the QD method achieves only a 2% improvement in efficiency, whereas the TL-PC-QD method yields a 73% efficiency gain.

Table II. Time summary in 2D Gd-bearing fuel assembly case.

Depletion method	PC	QD	TL – PC – QD
Time/s	3111.4	3051.2	1803.4
Accelerate ratio	/	1.02	1.73

4. CONCLUSIONS

The TL-PC-QD method incorporating post-correction has been implemented in the high-fidelity code NECP-X for the depletion calculations of Gd-bearing fuels. This method omits one transport calculation per burnup step, compared to the traditional PC method. Furthermore, by adopting a two-level predictor-corrector approach for the QD method, the number of substeps is significantly reduced.

The TL-PC-QD method demonstrates validated accuracy and computational efficiency across various cases. The QD method achieves nearly five times higher precision than the traditional PC method. Moreover, the TL-PC-QD method reduces the number of substeps from 100 to 5 while maintaining the accuracy, leading to a dramatic improvement in efficiency. This efficiency gain becomes more pronounced as the size of the problem increases.

Above all, when maintaining comparable accuracy, the TL-PC-QD method enables the burnup step size to be extended to more than twice that of the traditional PC method. Meanwhile, when the burnup step is kept identical, the TL-PC-QD method also achieves an efficiency over 1.5 times that of the traditional

PC method by omitting one transport calculation per step. Consequently, the computational efficiency of the TL-PC-QD method reaches nearly fourfold that of the traditional PC method.

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